

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EFL CLASSES

Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva

Student of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Mushtariy Tolibovna Qarshiyeva

2nd year student of Termiz State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7424050>

Abstract. *This article describes the importance of interactive learning technologies and methods in the modern educational process in the EFL classes, describes the advantages of this approach. It shows a number of techniques that educators use in their work.*

Keywords: *interactive technologies, educational process, foreign language, role play, problem lecture, new approach.*

РОЛЬ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В данной статье описывается значение интерактивных технологий и методов обучения в современном образовательном процессе на занятиях по английскому языку, описываются преимущества такого подхода. В ней показан ряд приемов, которые воспитатели используют в своей работе.*

Ключевые слова: *интерактивные технологии, учебный процесс, иностранный язык, ролевая игра, проблемная лекция, новый подход.*

Introduction: Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. Therefore, in order to teach this language more deeply in the educational system, pedagogues are required to make extensive use of innovative methods. For this reason, the introduction of the decision "On further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 is a clear proof of this. As a world language, English is becoming the most needed language in almost all fields. For this reason, not only in the educational system, but also in all spheres, with the full understanding that learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed times is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development, great attention is being paid to the importance of language. Like other fields, language learning also depends on the age of the students along with their minds.

Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing. This is because it is becoming more and more difficult to live without knowing English in the course of life. But language learning also depends on age. Scientists have even proven that children learn the language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn a language, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, the fact that children have more time than adults, and they keep the learned information in their memory quickly.

Currently, the desire to learn a language is very high, especially with the current information and communication tools, this situation shows high indicators. The conditions created by our state, the equipment of the classrooms with modern technologies, the provision of young educated personnel, the organization of television online classes on online TV channels for everyone to engage in independent activities outside of classes are commendable. Learners may not understand English grammar, lexis, phonetics, units, but they can master the language at

an excellent level through cartoons, games, and pictures. Accordingly, two types of methods are effectively used in grammar:

- Inductive method
- Deductive method

In the inductive method, grammatical rules are first explained to learners and then reinforced through examples. This method is often useful for advanced learners. For example, tenses, prepositions, articles are well-known terms for high-level learners, they can make sentences by adding possessive, participle, complement, and case parts.

In the deductive method, the topic is first introduced through certain games and exercises, and then it is explained based on the rules. It is more effective to explain the topic to them through games and songs, since elementary level learners do not have knowledge about possessors, participles, verbs and other units. For example, Can is a modal verb in English and is taught through handout materials.

- Can you play the piano?
- Can you open the window?
- It is very easy.
- Can you do it Lucy?

According to psychologists, compared to older people, children are 70-80% more interested in new things, eager to read and learn. Children try to perform tasks that they cannot perform even in our daily life despite warnings. They get bored of the sameness very quickly, therefore, it is necessary for the teaching staff to organize lessons in new ways, in an unconventional way, to fully create the environment of the foreign language being studied.

Therefore, teachers should organize lessons using interactive, innovative and interesting methods and technologies. The introduction of working with students individually, in groups and in pairs, in the form of various competitions, in the form of games, with the use of colorful visual aids, and to prepare separately for each lesson is required. This type of lessons increases love and interests for the language, activates inactive students, and creates healthy competition among students. Competition is the foundation of growth.

As Masaru Ibuka, one of the Chinese inventors, wrote in his famous book "After It's Too Late": "...a child's brain can hold an infinite amount of information...". It is also necessary to pay attention to the fact that children of 6-7 years old do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching the language to elementary school students learning English with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language, it can tire the learner and weaken his interest in language learning. Because teaching a foreign language to elementary school students is difficult and at the same time one of the responsible tasks. Therefore, the following innovative methods can be used to teach them English meaningfully and interestingly:

Visual learning - remembering information by seeing. It is known that young children remember the objects they see more than the information they hear. Therefore, it is necessary to teach new words through various visual aids, posters, by writing on objects that are visible and often used in everyday life and must make sentences with the new words they learned. For example, writing on a book, table, blackboard, pen, window, etc. Since such things are often seen and used in everyday life, the child learns these words involuntarily.

Singing words that are difficult to understand or remember through songs and poems. Along with remembering new words, the child's oral speech also develops. For example, it can be shown that children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing it. Language learning includes many competitive grammar and vocabulary games. In this, students perform various tasks given by the teacher. As a result, competition will arise among students, and their interest in learning the language will increase. After all, as Chinese thinkers say: "All human interests arise through competition."

Kinaesthetic learning - remembering information through actions. Also, mixed technique is where we can optionally combine different techniques. For example, learners can play games, sing songs, draw pictures, show new words through various actions. The advantage of the technique is diversity. In this, the student is not limited by only one thing.

Learning through cartoons. It is known that students are interested in watching different cartoons. In the process of watching cartoons in English, although he does not understand the words in the cartoon, he tries to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for students to learn the language.

Learning through senses (tasting vegetables, fruits, food, holding various objects, smelling flowers). Before studying this new method, it is worth quoting the opinions of a practicing psychologist: "A pedagogue who wants something to stick in the memory of students should try to involve as many of the student's sensory organs as possible in the process of memorizing: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations, and even the organs of smell and taste."

In fact, language learning through the senses is more useful and effective than other methods. For example, in the process of tasting a single apple, the student knows its color, taste, size, smell, and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children the English name of the colors, the children immediately remember the time when they ate the fruit. Therefore, the use of such methods helps the student to retain information in his memory for a long time.

Conclusion: By conclusion way, it should be noted that all interactive methods and technologies not only develop communicative skills, but can also stimulate the development of other skills. In addition, it helps to establish emotional connections between students, teaches them to work in a team, listen to the opinions of their peers, and establishes a closer relationship between students and the teacher. Practice shows that the use of interactive methods and technologies in a foreign language lesson relieves the nervous tension of students, allows them to change the forms of activity, to focus on the main issues of more and more effective engagement with the lesson. Ultimately, the quality of moral support and the efficiency of its acquisition will increase significantly, and as a result, the motivation of learners to learn a foreign language will increase.

REFERENCES

1. Bakhrom, K., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). THEORETICAL BASICS FOR ENGLISH TEACHING. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI, 157-158.
2. Bekmuratova U. B. "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012.

3. G. Djumambetova, B. Khabibullaeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 106-107. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7005635
4. Hoshimov O'. H, Yakubov I.Y.A. Methodology of teaching English. Tashkent-2003.
5. J. Richards and Th. S. Rodgers, Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching, Cambridge University Press, 2001.
6. Jumaeva Mukarrama, Azimov Jasurbek, & Saidov Kamoliddin. (2022). TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS IN ENGLISH. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(06), 252–255. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/HB7Y9>
7. Jumayeva, M. (2022). ISLOM MA'RIFATINING TA'LIM-TARBIYA SIVILIZATSIYASIGA TA'SIRI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(8), 41–44. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/3419>
8. Jumayeva, Mukarrama Bekzodovna (2022). OLIY TA'LIMDA INNOVATION USUL VA VOSITALAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (Special Issue 20), 214-226. doi: 10.24412/2181-1784-2022-20-214-226
9. M. Jumayeva (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B7), 711-714. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7264531
10. M. Jumayeva (2022). EFFECTIVE CREATIVE WAY OF ERKIN VAHIDOV. TRANSLATOR, POET, HERO OF UZBEKISTAN.. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 404-409. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7059373
11. M. Jumayeva (2022). UYG'ONISH DAVRI ALLOMALARINING PEDAGOGIKA VA TA'LIMTARBIYAGA O'ZGACHA YONDASHUV ASOSIDAGI QARASHLARI TAHLILI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 26-29. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6990805
12. M. Jumayeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF FEATURE FILMS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B7), 581-583. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7257719
13. M. Jumayeva, & M. Mahmudova (2022). INGLIZ TILIDA TALAFFUZNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 263-265. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7027100
14. M. Khodorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rikhsitlayeva. "Use of assistants in foreign language teaching". Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, 2005.
15. Maxmudjonov Ibroximjon, & Jumayeva Mukarrama. (2022). HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(5), 178–182. Retrieved from <https://involta.uz/index.php/iv/article/view/119>
16. Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva (2021). INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS. *Scientific progress*, 2 (4), 881-885.
17. Q. Khatamova, M.N. Mirzayeva. "Interactive methods used in English lessons" (methodical manual), Navoi - 2006, 40 pages.
18. R.Blair, Innovation approaches to language teaching, New York, Newbury House, 2010.
19. Stupina, S.B. Technologies of interactive learning in higher education. educational-methodical manual.

20. Turdieva Umidaxon, & Jumaeva Mukarrama. (2022). SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE AS A FACTOR IN DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM SPHERE. *Academic Research Journal*, 1(3), 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880388>
21. Umidjon, G., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). USED IN LESSON PROCESSES EFFICIENCY OF INTERACTIVE METHODS. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 161-162.